

ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION AND SMALL-SCALE ENTERPRISES GROWTH

CHRISTY OLUFUNMILAYO, ADERINTO

Bowen University, Iwo, Nigeria. Email: layoaderinto@gmail.com

ANTHONY ABIODUN, ENIOLA

Great Zimbabwe University, Zimbabwe. Email: aeniola@gzu.ac.zw

JOHNSON OLUSOLA, LAOSEBIKAN

Bowen University, Iwo, Nigeria. Email: johnson.laosebikan@bowen.edu.ng

DAVID OLUWATOYIN, OLOYEDE

Bowen University, Iwo, Nigeria. Email: toyin.loyede@bowen.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The paper investigated entrepreneurial innovation and small-scale business growth in Nigeria. A questionnaire-based research design was used in the study, which focused on small-scale enterprises in the areas of manufacturing, accommodation, food, and information and communication technology in the three southwestern states that comprised the population. Using Taro Yamani, a sample size of 1092 surveys was distributed across the three states, with a total number of 1022 retrieved and analyzed. The study used and tested the OECD's types of innovation. According to the study result from the multiple regression analysis, only product, organizational, and marketing innovations have a significantly positive relationship with small-scale enterprise growth, while process innovation has a moderately significant correlation. The study also recommends that small businesses invest more in process innovation, just as they do in product, marketing, and organizational innovation.

Keywords: Product, Process, Organizational, Marketing, Innovations, Entrepreneurial Growth, small-scale enterprises

INTRODUCTION

Small-scale enterprises make the largest contribution to employment generation and the provision of raw materials to large companies. They greatly contribute to alleviating poverty and help citizens improve their standard of living (Isiaka et al., 2017). As in developed countries, small-scale businesses are expected to grow into medium-scale or large-scale enterprises. Most industrialised nations in the world today attained technological advancement due to the establishment of small-scale enterprises in the past, which served as a technological take off and self-reliance (Eniola et al., 2022). Small-scale businesses have contributed immensely to technological advancement in many advanced countries and have brought the nations to the level of economic development they have attained so far. It has, however, been discovered that many of these small-scale enterprises in Nigeria are not growing as they should be (Faloye, 2015). Isiaka et al. (2017) said that most small businesses could not make it to maturity. Some are already dead, and others did not make it through the first five years.

A review of literature has shown that the ability of small business owners to innovate is a major factor that can enhance the growth and sustainability of small-scale businesses and reduce their failure rate. Various authors have written extensively in developed countries on innovation, especially as it relates to businesses, but studies on innovation in developing countries are still very few (Abdu & Jibri, 2017; Adebowale, Diyamett, Lema & Oyeyinka, 2014; Faloye, 2015; Egbetokun et al., 2009). This study is important because it adds to what is known about entrepreneurial innovation in developing countries. It also answers calls from researchers for more research on how entrepreneurial innovation affects the growth and longevity of small businesses.

Moreover, a considerable gap has been identified in the area of entrepreneurial innovation at firm level in Nigeria. A few studies Akosile, (2017)0; Faloye, (2015); Mohammed and Abimiku, (2015); Ayozie et al., (2013); Egbetokun et al., (2009) have looked at small businesses and how they innovate and grow (Akosile, 2017; Faloye, 2015; Mohammed & Abimiku, 2015; Ayozie et al., 2013; Egbetokun et al., 2009). In some instances, small and medium enterprises were studied together, but it is important to note that they are different in terms of size, operation, structure, etc., so the need to study them individually. This study therefore focused on small-scale enterprises because they constitute the larger part of business enterprises in southwestern Nigeria (SMEDAN & NBS, 2017). It is also important to remember that the recommendations that come out of studies of large or medium-sized businesses might not work for small businesses because of their size and how they work. There is therefore a need for more research on this, especially in Africa and Nigeria in particular.

It is necessary to understand the prevalent types of entrepreneurial innovation in small-scale enterprises. Schumpeter (1934) identified five types of innovation, namely new product innovation, new process innovation, market innovation, input or resource innovation, and organisational innovation, while Blank (2013) identified three types of innovation, namely disruptive innovation, breakthrough innovation, and incremental innovation. In line with Schumpeter's view, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2018), in its Oslo Manual, classified innovation into four categories: product innovation, organisational innovation, process innovation, and marketing innovation. This study adopted the OECD's types of innovation for further discussion and to objectively identify how the prevalent types of entrepreneurial innovation (product, process, marketing, and organisational innovations) being practised affect the growth of the small-scale enterprises in South West Nigeria.

LITERATURE

Schumpeter's theory of innovation contributed greatly to the concept of innovation and entrepreneurship. The theory posits that any business seeking growth must innovate, as innovation is an important factor in a business's competitiveness. The theory also posits that innovation leads to economic growth. Schumpeter categorised innovation into five types: product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, material innovation, and

organisational innovation. This theory is thought to be the most important one for this study because it has to do with business innovation and entrepreneurship.

Small-scale enterprises differ in sizes, modes of operations, organisational structures, management styles, etc. (Zivkovic & Benvada, 2014) and this makes it difficult to categorise their problems and growth patterns in a methodological way. However, growth is critical to small-scale enterprises because growth reduces their chances of closing business or total failure (Hayilom, 2020; Rauch & Rijkskik, 2013). Pasanen (2007) affirms that growth is connected to a firm's survival and accomplishment of its organisational goals, and this can be measured in line with employment, revenue, market share, profitability, and product development. Studies have shown that there is a great probability that small innovative businesses will grow faster than big organisations that do not innovate (Daunfeldt & Elert, 2013).

Innovation is a big word in the business world, and various authors have given definitions of the concept. Crossan and Apaydin (2010) defined innovation as the process of producing, adopting, assimilating, and exploitation of a value-added novelty in the economic and social environment, which also involves the improvement and increase in quality of products, services, and markets; as well as the development of novel ways of production; and the institution of novel management processes. For a business, Drucker (2006) noted that innovation has to do with bringing in novel visions, enhancement of services, or production of vibrant products. Several literature studies have found that product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, and organisational innovation help small businesses grow and survive (Chenge & Wang, 2020; Budiarto & Pramudiati, 2018; Rosli & Sidek, 2013; Ofosu & Dzisi, 2014; Egbetokun et al., 2010). This is in line with Bartelsman, Falk, Hagsten, and Polder (2019), who are of the view that product innovations are directly linked to business growth, especially in terms of productivity and a high profit ratio.

Empirically, Ukpabio et al. (2018) studied the effect of innovation on small businesses' growth in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the area of manufacturing in Nigeria. Precisely, the manufacturing businesses were into furniture, woodworking, textiles, clothing, leatherwork, footwear, industrial plastic and rubber businesses. 305 questionnaires were used to gather data from the business owners and managers, and the data obtained was analyzed through regression analysis and correlation analysis. The correlation result indicates that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria practise the four dimensions of innovation (product, process, market, and organizational), and the four types of entrepreneurial innovation have a significant positive relationship on the growth of SMEs as well as firm size, which was the control variable. But the result of the regression showed that both process innovation and organisational innovation have a big impact on small businesses.

Akinwale, Adepoju, and Olomu (2017) investigated the impact of product innovation, process innovation, and research and development expenditure on small and medium enterprises' performance in terms of profitability in the manufacturing industry in Nigeria. They used survey research, and 1000 small and medium enterprises were surveyed with a response rate of 52.1%. The findings showed that small and medium enterprises in Nigeria practise product and process innovations. The result also showed that research and development expenditure of

the firms as well as product and process innovation have a significant influence on the performance of the firms, especially in terms of profitability and growth, with a probability value of 0.0529, 0.0624, and 0.0086, respectively, at the 10% level of significance.

Kiveu (2017) conducted research in Kenya on manufacturing small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Using Schumpeter's theory of entrepreneurship and innovation, the study investigated the effects of product, process, marketing, and organisational innovations on firm competitiveness. A survey design with a descriptive-explanatory research design was used. A semi-structured questionnaire was designed and administered to 284 enterprises from three industrial clusters. The collected data was looked at using descriptive and inferential statistics, and a multiple linear regression model was used to look at the relationship between innovation and a company's ability to compete. Findings from the study showed that small and medium-scale enterprises in Nairobi, Kenya practise product, process, organizational, and marketing innovations. The study also found that all four types of innovation—product, process, marketing, and organizational—helped the firm be more competitive. The study also found that the relationship between innovation and competitiveness was significantly changed by the size of the firm.

Soto-Acosta, Popa and Palacios-Marques (2015) analyzed the impact of organisational innovation on e-business innovation in small and medium-scale enterprises in Spain. The small and medium-scale enterprises investigated were into manufacturing. They specifically investigated the relationship between e-business and business growth, using organisational innovation as a moderating variable. Using an integrative research model, a total of 1291 businesses with at least 15 employees in the manufacturing sector in Southeast Spain were found and contacted to take part in the survey. Their findings revealed that small and medium enterprises in Spain practise organisational innovation more and their findings also showed that organisational innovation has a significant positive influence and contributes positively to firm growth. Therefore, this study hypothesises that

There is no association between product, process, marketing, and organizational innovations by entrepreneurs and the small businesses growth in South West Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out quantitatively in the small-scale industries of manufacturing, accommodation and food services, and information and communication technology in the southwestern states of Lagos, Oyo, and Osun. One of the reasons for choosing the states is that the states have the largest dominant small-scale industry in the country. Using a 95 percent confidence level, a total sample size of 1,092 among small-scale enterprises was obtained using Taro Yamani (Osun: 332, Oyo: 377, and Lagos: 383) from a total population of 17076 across the three different states. A 1092 survey was distributed across the three states with a total number of 1022 retrieved from the respondents, which represents 93.58% of the total. The study instrument adopted was a structured questionnaire. The instrument contained Likert-type scale items using SPSS 25 to analyse. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the instrument's reliability, as explained below.

Reliability and Normality Test

For a construct to be reliable, the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient must be greater than or equal to 0.7 and 0.80 as specified in the general threshold. The results indicated that innovation (DI) 0.787, entrepreneurial innovation (EI) 0.878, product innovation (PI) 0.721, process innovation (ProcI) 0.727, organization innovation (OI) 0.795, marketing innovation (MI) 0.722, and small-scale enterprise growth (SSEG) 0.876. The results showed that all constructs are within the benchmark set for reliability has been satisfied. The normality test for this study was carried out using kurtosis. A normality test was done to see if the dependent variable (Small Scale Growth) had a distribution that would work with the statistical method. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was done, and the results showed that the distribution of the dependent variable (Small Scale Growth) has a P-value higher than 0.05. As a result, there is compelling evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H₀). Since the variable has a normal distribution, it can be further analyzed.

Component Analysis

Four components were retrieved using the principal component analysis (PCA) for the investigation. The percentage of variance that could be explained by an underlying component was determined by the KMO measure of sample adequacy. The KMO is 0.958 and the p-value for the study's factor analysis is 0.05. The findings state that the KMO value should be between 0.8 and 1, and since it is within this range, the sampling is deemed appropriate. The sphericity of the variables is also confirmed by the Bartlett's test, which also confirms their independence. This hypothesis will be rejected if the factor model has a p value of less than 0.05, which indicates that it is appropriate. The analysis indicate that $p = 0.05$, implying that the component model is valid.

DESCRIPTIVE AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Four types of entrepreneurial innovation were examined in the study, which included product, process, organizational, and marketing. As regards product innovation, the identification of customers' needs in the development of new products (mean=3.86, SD=0.974); introduction of new products in the last five years (mean=3.72, SD=0.974); improvement of existing products (mean=3.72, SD=0.974); and installation of new equipment and machineries (mean=3.58, SD=1.007) were the product innovations engaged in by these small-scale businesses.

Moreover, the introduction of new technologies in the product process (mean = 3.64, SD = 0.977); investment in research and development (mean = 3.66, SD = 0.851); and new methods of operation (mean = 3.67, SD = 0.945) were the process innovations identified in the study. External collaboration and relationships with other firms (mean = 3.73, SD = 0.937); good relationships with their customers (mean = 3.85, SD = 0.924); entrepreneurial innovation has helped redefine their management structure, system, culture, and job design (mean = 3.82, SD = 0.916); skills and learning abilities of the owners and managers (mean = 3.90, SD = 0.873);

and visions of the owners and managers (mean = 3.89, SD = 0.929) were the organisational innovation engaged in by these small-scale businesses. The study also found that these small businesses came up with new ways to get their products to customers (mean = 3.97, SD = 0.873), new ways to package and design their products (mean = 3.84, SD = 0.977), and new markets (mean = 3.90, SD = 0.969).

Table 1: Entrepreneurial Innovation on Small Scale Enterprise Growth

Analysis	Assessment			
R correlation coefficient	0.671			
R² coefficient of determination	0.45			
R² Adjusted	0.447			
F stat (4,1017)	207.691			
Sig.	0.000***			
	Unstandardized β coefficient	Standardized β coefficient	t-statistic	Sig.
Constant	1.081		9.823	.000
PI	.265	.265	9.489	.000
Procl	.028	.028	.916	.360
OI	.149	.154	5.094	.000
MI	.342	.386	13.698	.000

Source: Researchers

The multiple linear regression analysis was carried out as shown in Table 1, to determine the influence of the types of entrepreneurial innovation on small-scale enterprise growth. The results showed that entrepreneurial innovation has a positive, high and statistically significant relationship with small-scale enterprise growth ($r=0.67$, $p<0.05$). Furthermore, the R squared value of 0.45 obtained from the results showed that entrepreneurial innovation explains 45% variation in small-scale enterprise growth. This means that the change in small-scale enterprise growth is explained by entrepreneurial innovation up to 45%. It was discovered that product, process, organizational and marketing innovations have positive effect on small-scale enterprise growth. Furthermore, a significant statistical concept for small-scale enterprise growth was developed ($F(4,1017)=207.691$, $p<0.005$). Moreover, the estimated regression beta coefficient indicated that process innovations ($=0.03$, $p>0.05$) also exhibit a minimal positive statistically significant impact on small-scale enterprise growth, organizational ($=0.15$, $p<0.05$), product ($=0.27$, $p<0.05$), and marketing ($=0.34$, $p<0.05$) innovations indicate positive statistically significant effects on small-scale enterprise growth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The four types of entrepreneurial innovation identified were product innovation, process innovation, organisational innovation, and marketing innovation. However, the majority of small-scale business owners and managers practise product, organizational, and marketing innovations, while few of them practise process innovation. This finding is consistent with Ukpabio et al. (2018) as their findings revealed that small-scale enterprises in the area of

manufacturing in Nigeria do practise product, process, organizational, and marketing innovations. All the proxies of the four types of innovations also align with this study. It is, however, contrary to Obunike and Udu (2018), whose results revealed that small-scale enterprises in manufacturing in Nigeria practised only product and process innovation. The finding could be so because Obunike and Udu (2018)'s study was limited to only Lagos State. This result is also consistent with Kiveu (2017) as his findings revealed that small-scale enterprises in Nairobi do practise all four types of innovation. This finding also aligns with Efstathiades et al. (2007) as their findings showed that small-scale enterprises in the food and beverage industry in Cyprus practised all four types of entrepreneurial innovation.

For product innovation, the proxies examined include the identification of customers' needs in the development of new products; the introduction of new products in the last five years; the improvement of existing products; and the installation of new equipment and machineries. Although the identification of customers' needs in the development of new products ranked the highest factor under product innovation, all other factors also showed high means and this aligns with Ukpabio et al (2018). Looking at the identification of customers' needs, this goes in line with one of the dimensions of lean startup, which is the capability to understand customers and users deeply. When making new products or improving old ones, it puts the needs of potential customers' first. Identification of customers' needs helps entrepreneurs to avoid costly failures in production innovation. This fits with what Harms and Schwery (2019) say which is that figuring out what customers want in terms of what they know helps improve product innovation.

For process innovation, some factors considered include the introduction of new technologies in the product process, investment in research and development, and new methods of operation. The quantitative findings revealed that all the factors considered recorded high means, indicating that the introduction of new technologies, investment in research and development, and new methods of operation are crucial in process innovation. The finding is consistent with prior studies. In their study of the impact of different forms of innovation on small-scale enterprises in Kosovo, Mahmutaj and Krasniqi (2020) identified new methods of operation and new machinery and equipment as essential factors in process innovation. Likewise, Ukpabio et al. (2018) in their study of manufacturing small-scale enterprises in Nigeria reported that investment in research and development, new methods of operation, and the introduction of new technologies are important in process innovation. In another study in Tanzania by Ndesaulwa and Kikula (2016), it was reported that new methods of operation, the introduction of new technologies, and involvement in research and development are factors in process innovation. Martin and Namusonge (2014) in their study of nine garment manufacturing small-scale businesses in Kenya also affirmed that the introduction of new technologies is an important factor in process innovation. Small-scale businesses use new technologies, better ways of making things, investments in research and development, and the purchase of new tools and machines to improve their efficiency by cutting down on costs and waste.

For organisational innovation, factors considered are external collaboration and relationships with other firms and good relationships with their customers; management structure, system,

and culture; job design skills and learning abilities of owners and managers; and visions of owners and managers. The study ascertained that small-scale enterprises in the South West of Nigeria engaged in all the factors of organisational innovation as all the factors had high means, although skills and learning abilities of owners and managers ranked highest. The finding is in agreement with Ukpabio et al. (2018) and Razavi and Attarnezhad (2013) that reported that management structure, system, culture, job design, skills and learning abilities of owners, visions of owners and managers, and collaboration with external networks are important factors in organisational innovation. However, Kiveu (2017) in his study found management structure and systems as important factors in organisational innovation.

Lastly, factors considered in marketing innovation include the introduction of new distribution channels, the introduction of new packaging and product designs, and the discovery of new markets. Findings revealed that all the factors are considered significant in marketing innovation, although the introduction of new distribution channels ranked highest. This finding aligns with Mahmutaj and Krasniqi (2020), Ukpabio et al. (2018) and Efstathiades et al. (2007).

CONCLUSION

The study also concludes that small-scale enterprises should engage more in process innovation just as they do for product innovation, marketing innovation, and organisational innovation. For product innovation, identification of customers' needs, improvement of existing products, and installation of new equipment and machinery are to be considered in the development of new products to facilitate an increase in market share and profitability. While the skills and learning ability of the owners and managers of small-scale enterprises, their external collaboration and relationships with other firms, and good relationships with customers are highly considered important in organisational innovation to promote profitability.

The study was limited due to delays experienced while collecting data due to the uncooperative attitude of some of the respondents in divulging certain information about their business, especially as it relates to revenue and profitability. Further studies can be conducted to investigate other areas of businesses like entertainment and recreation businesses, real estate businesses, agriculture businesses, and logistic businesses, which are growing faster now in Nigeria.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they do not have any known personal or financial relationships that could be seen to have influenced the work in this paper.

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